

Synthesis and Characterisation of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Manganese(II) and Copper(II) with 2-Amino-3-hydroxypyridine and some Nitrogen Donors

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2-Amino-3-hydroxypyridine (AHP) has a versatile chelating ability with metal ions¹. Its binary complexes with some metal ions have been prepared in our laboratory², but so far, no work has been done on its mixed ligand metal complexes. The present work deals with the syntheses of Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} mixed ligand complexes with AHP and some N-donor ligands NH₃/CH₃NH₂/C₂H₅NH₂/Py.

Results and Discussion

The mixed ligand complexes have been assigned the compositions as based on elemental analyses (Table 1). The molar conductance values indicate that the Mn^{II} complexes (2.1–3.5 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) are non-ionic while the Cu^{II} complexes (30.0–31.0 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) are 1 : 1 electrolytes³.

which can be attributed to the simultaneous deprotonation and formation of M–O bond at 3-position of AHP. M–O bonding is further confirmed due to the presence of a band at 400–440 cm⁻¹ (M–O)⁴. The ν_{NH} symmetric band at 3 125 cm⁻¹ is shifted to lower side by 40–30 cm⁻¹, indicating that N of amino group at 2-position is coordinated to metal atom. A band at 350–360 cm⁻¹ (M–N)^{4,5} is found in complexes. Appearance of a band at 3 225–3 250 cm⁻¹ (NH) in the complexes indicates coordination of NH₃/CH₃NH₂/C₂H₅NH₂. In case of the mixed ligand complexes of pyridine, a change in band of characteristic ring vibration (~1 460 cm⁻¹) of pyridine to higher frequencies, suggests that nitrogen of pyridine is bonded with the metal atom⁶. In case of the copper complexes the broad band at 1 400 cm⁻¹ is assigned to uncoordinated nitrate^{7,8}.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd* / (Colour, yield%)	Analysis % Found/(Calcd)			
	M	C	H	N
Mn(L ₁) ₂ (NH ₃) ₂ (Brown, 70)	27.79 (27.77)	60.58 60.60	5.56 5.55	14.20 14.14
Mn(L ₁) ₂ (CH ₃ NH ₂) ₂ (Brown, 67)	16.37 (16.41)	42.98 42.97	5.93 5.97	25.12 25.07
Mn(L ₁) ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ NH ₂) ₂ (Brown, 68)	15.12 (15.15)	46.31 46.28	6.60 6.61	23.19 23.14
Mn(L ₁) ₂ (Py) ₂ (Brown, 70)	12.80 (12.76)	55.60 55.68	4.59 4.64	19.47 19.48
[Cu(L ₁)(NH ₃) ₂] ₂ NO ₃ (Black, 70)	23.63 (23.66)	22.36 22.34	4.03 4.09	20.83 20.85
[Cu(L ₁)(CH ₃ NH ₂) ₂] ₂ NO ₃ (Black, 70)	21.41 (21.43)	28.36 28.33	5.02 5.06	23.65 23.60
[Cu(L ₁)(C ₂ H ₅ NH ₂) ₂] ₂ NO ₃ (Black, 68)	19.54 (19.58)	33.31 33.28	5.89 5.85	21.58 21.56
[Cu(L ₁)(Py) ₂] ₂ NO ₃ (Black, 70)	16.16 (16.19)	45.88 45.85	3.83 3.82	17.87 17.83

*HL₁ = AHP

The ir spectral bands of AHP at 3 425, 3 375 and 3 125 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν_{OH} (O–H...N), ν_{NH} asymmetric and ν_{NH} symmetric vibrations respectively. In the complexes, the ν_{OH} band of AHP (3 425 cm⁻¹) disappears,

The electronic spectra of the Mn^{II} mixed ligand complexes exhibit four weak bands at 30 510–30 580, 29 100–29 200, 24 100–24 180 and 20 220–20 290, corresponding to ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g} (⁴G), ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴E_g (⁴G), ⁴A_{1g}, (⁴G), ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴E_g (⁴D) and ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g} (⁴P) transitions respectively. These transitions are characteristic of octahedral geometry around manganese(II)^{8,9}. The spectra of the mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II} show a broad band at 17 920–17 950 cm⁻¹. This broad band is a combination of ²B₁ → ²A_{1g} and ²B_{1g} → ²E_g and is suggestive of a square-planar arrangement around copper(II)¹⁰.

Values of g_{av} calculated from the esr spectra of Mn(L₁)₂(L₂)₂, HL₂ = AHP, L₂ = NH₃/CH₃NH₂/C₂H₅NH₂/Py are respectively 2.0460, 2.0458, 2.0456, 2.0466 and for Cu(L₁)(L₂)₂NO₃, 2.2294, 2.2290, 2.2288, 2.2300. These values are indicative of some M–L covalent character.

¹H nmr spectra of the mixed ligand complexes are presented in Table 2. The chemical shift values of the main groups associated with AHP reveal that there is bonding of metal ion through oxygen after deprotonation of OH group of AHP. There are resonance signals in the spectra due to second nitrogen donor ligand.

From the above studies, the structure of mixed ligand complexes of Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} can be given as (I) and (II) respectively.

TABLE 2—PROTON CHEMICAL SHIFTS (δ ppm) OF SOME IMPORTANT GROUPS OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES*

Group	Mn(L ₁) ₂ (NH ₃) ₂	Mn(L ₁) ₂ (CH ₃ NH ₂) ₂	Mn(L ₁) ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ NH ₂)	Mn(L ₁) ₂ (Py) ₂
NH ₂	6.59 (bs)	6.59 (bs)	6.59 (bs)	6.59 (bs)
Pyridine ring	7.99 (m)	7.99 (m)	7.99 (m)	7.99 (m)
NH ₃	3.40 (s)	—	—	—
CH ₃	—	3.30 (t)	1.26 (t)	—
CH ₂	—	—	3.76 (q)	—
NH ₂	—	2.80 (q)	2.80 (t)	—
Py	—	—	—	8.00 (m)
	[Cu(L ₁)(NH ₃) ₂] ₂ NO ₃	[Cu(L ₁)(CH ₃ NH ₂) ₂] ₂ NO ₃	[Cu(L ₁)(C ₂ H ₅ NH ₂) ₂] ₂ NO ₃	[Cu(L ₁)(Py) ₂] ₂ NO ₃
NH ₂	6.57 (bs)	6.57 (bs)	6.57 (bs)	6.57 (bs)
Pyridine ring	8.03 (m)	8.03 (m)	8.03 (m)	8.03 (m)
NH ₃	3.40 (s)	—	—	—
CH ₃	—	2.13 (t)	1.24 (t)	—
CH ₂	—	—	3.76 (q)	—
NH ₂	—	2.60 (q)	2.60 (t)	—
Py	—	—	—	8.00 (m)

*HL₁ = AHP, bs = broad singlet, q = quartet, m = medium, t = triplet, s = singlet.

Experimental

All reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Solutions of different reagents were prepared in double-distilled water. The solutions of manganese(II) nitrate/copper(II) nitrate, AHP (Aldrich) and a N-donor ligand were mixed in the molar ratio, 1:2:2 in case of Mn^{II} and 1:1:2 in case of Cu^{II}, making the total volume ~50 ml. The contents were refluxed on a water bath for ~1.5 h. On concentrating and cooling, the complexes separated out which were washed and dried.

The metals were estimated following standard methods. Analyses for C and H were performed in microanalytical laboratory. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldhal's method. Molar conductances in nitrobenzene solution (10^{-3} M) were measured on a Toshniwal conductometer. Electronic spectra (nujol) were run on a Beckman DU-64 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 601 spectrophotometer, nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Bruker

MSL-300 FT-NMR spectrometer and esr spectra on a Varian spectrometer at room temperature (30°) using standard DPPH at a g value of 2.

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